

Table S2 Determined textural properties of materials.

Material	S_{BET} ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	$S_{\text{BET, Roq}}^*$ ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	S_{meso}^{**} ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	V_{micro}^{**} ($\text{mm}^3_{\text{liq}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	V_{micro}^{***} ($\text{mm}^3_{\text{liq}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	V_{net} ($\text{mm}^3_{\text{liq}} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Character of material
g-C ₃ N ₄	119	119	141	0	46	466	Meso-macroporous with small amount of micropores
Na(0.01)-CN	110	109	123	0	43	407	Macroporous with small amount of micropores
Na(0.02)-CN	100	95	116	0	39	416	Macroporous with small amount of micropores

* Since materials contain micropores, the value of specific surface area $S_{\text{BET, Roq}}$ is more correct/relevant instead of standard BET value.

** Determined using the t-plot.

** Determined by using the Horwath-Kawazoe solution.